

Mixed-ligand oxovanadium(IV) complexes with *N*-benzene sulfonyl-L-aspartic acid and 2,2'-bipyridine and 1,10-phenanthroline

Tapas Ghosh

Department of Chemistry, R. K. Mission V. C. College, P.O. Rahara, Kolkata-700 118, India

E-mail : ictg_64@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 28 October 2003, revised 22 April 2004, accepted 11 June 2004

N-Benzene sulfonyl-L-aspartic acid (hereafter, H₃L) in the presence of 2,2'-bipyridine or 1,10-phenanthroline (hereafter, B) on reaction with VOSO₄ in aqueous-ethanolic medium at pH ~4.5 afforded complexes of the type [V^{IV}O(HL)(B)(H₂O)]. H₃L acts as a bidentate dinegative ligand and coordinates the metal through the one deprotonated carboxylate-O and deprotonated amide-N leaving the other carboxylic acid group free. The complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses, magnetic susceptibility measurements and by IR and UV-vis spectroscopic techniques. The complexes are one electron paramagnetic ($\mu_{\text{eff}} \approx 1.73$ B.M.) at room temperature. V=O stretching frequency indicated the hexacoordinated environment around the metal center. They exhibit two ligand-field transitions in the visible region.

Among the twenty or so, biologically important naturally occurring amino acids, aspartic acid (asp) is characterized by the presence of two carboxyl functions which make it potentially tridentate ligand with a variety of coordination modes¹⁻⁴. In highly hydrated complex it behaves like glycine offering bidentate N, O-chelation⁴ as in [Cu(asp)(bipy)(H₂O)].3H₂O and in the low hydrated complex, the second carboxyl group in the β -position with respect to amine function is also involved in the metal coordination as in [Cu(asp)(im)(H₂O)₂], (im = imidazole) giving rise to polymeric species³.

The substitution of an Ar-SO₂ group on the amine nitrogen decreases the affinity of amino group for the metal ion and leads its coordination modes to be metal and pH dependent. At low pH the only binding site is the carboxyl group irrespective of the metal ion involved. With a view to study the binding mode of *N*-benzene sulfonyl-L-aspartic acid with VO²⁺ ion in presence of 2,2'-bipyridine or 1,10-phenanthroline, this work has been done and the results have been discussed in this paper.

Results and discussion

The prime ligand used in this work is the *N*-benzene sulfonyl-L-aspartic acid (hereafter, H₃L, having three replaceable hydrogen atom). 2,2'-Bipyridine (bipy) and 1,10-phenanthroline (phen)(hereafter, B) were used as secondary ligands. Reaction of VOSO₄ with H₃L and B in equimolar ratios in presence of two equivalent sodium acetate in aqueous-ethanolic medium gives complexes [V^{IV}O(HL)(bipy)(H₂O), 1] and [V^{IV}O(HL)(phen)(H₂O), 2].

The reaction can be represented by the following equation :

The complexes are not soluble in common organic solvents.

The magnetic susceptibility (1.71 B.M. and 1.74 B.M. respectively) indicate presence of one unpaired electron only in these complexes.

Complexes display strong V=O stretching frequencies 966 and 975 cm⁻¹. The disappearance of $\nu(\text{NH})$ (at 3250 cm⁻¹ in the free ligand) and the shift of antisymmetric and symmetric $\nu(\text{SO}_2)$ toward low energy (1320 and 1157 cm⁻¹, respectively in the complexes and 1350 and 1170 cm⁻¹, respectively in the free ligand) support the coordination of amide-N with deprotonation^{5,6}. The band near 848 cm⁻¹ is assigned to $\nu(\text{SN})$ ⁶. The appearance of a band near 1610 cm⁻¹ is assigned to the coordinated carboxylate group⁷ and the band near 1723 cm⁻¹ is assigned to the undissociated free carboxylic acid group (in the α - and β -positions with respect to amine function, respectively). The tribasic nature of *N-p*-toluene sulfonyl-L-glutamic acid (which also contains two carboxyl groups and one sulfonamide hydrogen like the *N*-benzene sulfonyl-L-aspartic acid) has been reported by Saladini *et al.*^{5,8}. The presence of a broad band⁹ near 3430 cm⁻¹ indicated the presence of coordinated water molecule.

The greenish-yellow to orange complexes (1 and 2) display two ligand-field transitions in DMSO solution in the visible region : 776–824 nm and 446–460 nm due to ²B_{2g}

$\rightarrow {}^2E_g$ and ${}^2B_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{1g}$ transitions, respectively¹⁰. Strong absorptions at higher energies vitiate the other possible transition ${}^2B_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$. The molar extinction coefficient (ϵ) values are comparatively large for *d-d* transitions and this is probably due to the distortion from perfect octahedral geometry.

Conclusion :

It appears from this study that in the presence of ligands bipy and phen, H_3L behaves as dinegative bidentate ligand and binds with VO^{2+} through the deprotonated one carboxylate-O and deprotonated amide-N atoms leaving the other potential donor carboxylic acid group uncoordinated forming a stable five-membered chelate ring leading to the formation of monomeric species. The dissociation of amide proton at a low pH ~ 4.5 is probably due to the σ -donor and π -acidic character of B ligands which increases the acidity of the amide proton through the formation of a stable $[VO(B)]^{2+}$ intermediate like Cu^{2+} system¹¹.

Experimental

Materials :

$VOSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$, L(-)aspartic acid and benzene sulfonyl chloride were obtained from Loba chemical company, India. 2,2'-Bipyridine and 1,10-phenanthroline, sodium acetate trihydrate were procured from E. Merck. All other materials were of A.R. grade and were used as received. H_3L was synthesized by a literature method¹².

Preparation of the metal complexes :

Both the complexes were prepared in the same fashion.

$[V^{IV}O(HL)(bipy)(H_2O)]$, 1 :

H_3L (0.15 g, 0.55 mmol), bipy (0.086 g, 0.55 mmol) were dissolved in 20 ml aqueous-ethanol (50%, v/v) on warming. Then added dropwise aqueous solution (5 ml) of $VOSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ (0.14 g, 0.55 mmol) followed by the addition of aqueous solution (5 ml) of sodium acetate trihydrate (0.15 g, 1.1 mmol). The reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h at $\sim 60^\circ$. Then added 10 ml ethanol and kept for slow evaporation at room temperature. A greenish-yellow product was obtained after one week. It was filtered, thoroughly washed with water, water-ethanol (50%, v/v) and dried over $CaCl_2$ (fused). Yield : 0.125 g (49%). For $[V^{IV}O(HL)(bipy)(H_2O)]$ Found (Calcd.) : C, 46.35 (46.87); H, 3.68 (3.71); N 8.18 (8.20) and For $[V^{IV}O(HL)(phen)(H_2O)]$ Found (Calcd.) : C, 48.95 (49.25); H, 3.50 (3.54); N, 7.81 (7.84).

Physical measurements :

Electronic spectra (in DMSO) were recorded on a Hitachi U-3501 spectrophotometer and IR spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 782 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured using a PAR model 155 vibrating sample magnetometer fitted with a Walker Scientific L75 FBAL magnet using $Hg[Co(SCN)_4]$ as the calibrant. A Perkin-Elmer CHNS/O analyzer 2400 was employed to obtain microanalytical data.

Acknowledgement

Financial assistance from U.G.C. (India) is gratefully acknowledged. Thanks are due to Prof. G. N. Mukherjee, Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, 92, A. P. C. Road, Kolkata for UV-vis spectra.

References

1. A. C. Evans, R. Guevremont and D. Rabenstein, in H. Sigel and A. Sigel (eds.), "Metal Ions in Biological Systems", Marcel Dekker, New York, 1979, Vol. 9, p. 41.
2. W. L. Kwik, K. P. Ang and G. Chen, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1980, **42**, 303.
3. L. Antolini, G. Marcotrigiano, L. Menabue, G. C. Pellacani and M. Saladini, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1982, **21**, 2263.
4. L. Antolini, G. Marcotrigiano, L. Menabue and G. C. Pellacani, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1983, **22**, 141.
5. A. B. Corradi, G. Lusvardi, L. Menabue, M. Saladini and P. Sagarabotto, *Polyhedron*, 1999, **18**, 1975.
6. A. B. Corradi, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1992, **117**, 45.
7. S. P. Rath, S. Mondal and T. Ghosh, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1996, **21**, 309; S. Bhattacharya and T. Ghosh, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2002, **27**, 89; S. Mondal, S. Dutta and A. Chakravorty, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1995, 1115.
8. M. Bosari, L. Menabue and M. Saladini, *Polyhedron*, 1999, **18**, 1983.
9. M. R. Maurya, S. Khurana, C. Schulzke and D. Rehder, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2002, 779; J. K. Nag, D. Das, S. Pal and C. Sinha, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 2001, **113**, 11.
10. C. J. Ballhausen and H. B. Gray, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **1**, 111.
11. L. P. Battaglia, G. B. Gavioli, A. B. Corradi, M. Borsari, L. Menabue, G. Pelosi, M. Saladini and M. Sola, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1990, 91.
12. "Vogel's Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", ELBS with Longman, U.K., 1994, p. 1275.